

Comparative Study of EVA and Waste Polymer Modified Bitumen

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Abstract : Abstract- Polymer-modified bitumen are used to combat different pavement distresses and to increase the life span of pavement. Unmodified bitumen cannot perform better with the range extreme minimum and maximum pavement temperatures. The polymers commonly used to modify the bitumen are ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA) styrene butadiene styrene (SBS). The aim this study to compare the performance of bitumen modified bitumen EVA with the bitumen modified by waste low density polyethylene(LDPE), polypropylene (PP) obtained from waste carry bags and waste tyre rubber (CR) to encourage the use of waste polymer whose disposal is big problem today, in place of costly virgin polymer. From the experimental study it was found that waste polymers are also effective in improving the properties bitumen as that of virgin polymer

Keywords : Keywords- Waste plastic, LDPE, PP, Modified bitumen, EVA

Conference Title : ICEP 2014 : International Conference on Electronic Publications

Conference Location : journal city, WASET

Conference Dates : November 23-23, 2014